

Software Management Plan Template

Version 2023

Introduction

Open Science, software quality and software sustainability are key elements in eScience Center projects. They enable verification, reproducibility, and transparency in all phases of the research process, and maximize the chance for adoption, reuse and impact of software created in the projects.

Our Research Software Engineers put substantial effort into creating open, high-quality, sustainable software. To allow community contributions and adoption of the software by others, all software will use permissive open-source licences (research software developed by the eScience Center will be licensed under the Apache 2.0 licence) and source code will be published in publicly accessible repositories such as GitHub.

In addition, the project software will align with the FAIR4RS software principles¹ and be made available in the Research Software Directory². This makes the software findable for search engines, enables software citation and adds relevant metadata such as information on authorship, documentation, related projects, tools and publications.

The long-term sustainability of the software developed in eScience Center projects is the responsibility of the Lead Applicant. This template should be used to describe the measures that will be taken, both during and after the project, to ensure the usability and availability of the software beyond the duration of the project itself. These measures may be taken directly by the Lead Applicant, project partners or their institutes, but we strongly suggest to also involve external organizations and/or communities.

The questions that follow should be interpreted in the broadest sense, as there is no one-size-fits-all solution for long-term software sustainability. However, you should describe each of the measures as concretely as possible. In each case you should specify which action will be taken at which moment; likewise, in each case you should make clear with whom or with which institute the responsibility for ensuring sustainability lies. It is encouraged, though not required, to make these responsibilities explicit in the form of one or more letters of support.

This SMP follows the requirements from the Practical Guide to Software Management Plans³, co-developed by the eScience Center and the National Research Council (NWO).

If you do not personally possess the expertise to fill out this SMP, please consult your local digital competence centre or other appropriate experts.

All blue italic text contains instructions. This text may be deleted before submission.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>

² <https://research-software-directory.org/>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038280>

Required Questions

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended user community.

Some aspects to be considered:

- *What is the purpose of the software?*
- *What is the software's intended user community?*
- *If you are not reusing existing software, please explain why.*

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2. Which version control system will you use to manage your source code?

By default, the eScience Center uses git and public GitHub repositories. Please state if there is any reason to manage version control in a different way for your project.

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3. How will you make your software publicly available? Please provide links to the software if this is already the case.

Software created in eScience Center projects is always made publicly available using GitHub, the Research Software Directory and Zenodo, unless explicitly agreed otherwise before the submission of the proposal.

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4. What licence will your software have?

The eScience Center uses the Apache-2 licence for all software we create. The use of a different licence must be explicitly agreed upon before submission of the proposal. Please contact us if there is any reason for using a different licence, for example because existing software or libraries will be used with an incompatible licence (such as GPL).

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5. What measures will be taken during the project to ensure the long-term sustainability of the software developed in the project? (max. 300 words)

Some examples include:

- *A researcher or RSE from a research institute is allocated to the project to co-develop the software during the project and help maintain it afterwards.*
- *A community will co-develop the software and help maintain it afterwards.*
- *Organizing workshops and hands-on user training to create or extend a community around the software.*
- *The software will be developed as part of an overarching software suite used in other (research) projects.*
- *A commercial partner interested in exploiting the software is included as co-applicant on the basis of a concrete in-cash or in-kind investment.*

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6. What measures will be taken to support the software after completion of the project? (max. 300 words)

Some examples include:

- *The software is hosted by an institute and a user support desk is made available for a certain period.*
- *The software is integrated into a research infrastructure based on a large community.*
- *A commercial partner or spin-off will continue the support and development of the software.*

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7. What resources are needed to ensure the long-term usability and availability of the software, and how will these resources be funded or obtained? (max. 300 words)

Some examples include:

- *Storage or compute infrastructure to host the software.*
- *RSEs to maintain the software and support the community that uses it.*

- *A user support desk.*

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8. Are there other measures that will be taken to promote the software's longevity? (max. 300 words)

Some examples include:

- *Additional project proposals which will help to further develop the software.*
- *The software is integrated into teaching in a course on the Bachelor or Master level.*
- *Outreach through mainstream media such as newspaper articles, blogs, YouTube videos, tweets, etc.*

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Optional Questions

The remaining questions in this SMP are typically answered during the kick-off phase of an eScience Center project by the project team, including the eScience Center RSEs working on the project. This typically leads to an update of the SMP.

If some of these questions can be answered during the application phase, we encourage you to do so.

9. How will your software be documented? Please provide a link to the documentation, if available.

Software will be documented for different users (user documentation, developer documentation). If you have any (additional) plans on how your software will be documented (e.g. creating tutorials, incorporating it in teaching, etc.) please specify.

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10. How will your software document its installation requirements? Please provide a link to the installation documentation, if available.

Explain system requirements (e.g. dependencies) for deploying the software and instructions for installation and testing.

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11. How will you enable citation of your software by users? Please provide a link to software citation data and/or DOI if available.

The eScience Center uses the Citation File Format (CFF) to provide citation metadata for software, and Zenodo to provide DOIs for software releases. Please specify if there are reasons to use a different approach.

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12. How will your software be tested? Please provide a link to automated testing results, if available.

Explain how you will incorporate tests to ensure your software works and continues to work as intended. Different types of testing (unit, functional, integration, linting, typing, regression, etc.) could be used. Coverage tools should also be used to assess the extent of the tested code.

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13. How will your software be packaged and distributed? Please provide a link to available packaging information (e.g. entry in a packaging registry, if available).

Use appropriate package managers to allow users to install/deploy your software with ease. Examples include PyPI, CRAN, NPM, Maven, Crates, conda, etc.

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The authors of this document will ensure that this Software Management Plan is carried out as specified above.

Name: ...

Affiliation: ...

Date: ...

(please copy this section if needed)